

WEIBULL FIBRE STRENGTH PARAMETERS DETERMINED BY SINGLE FIBRE FRAGMENTATION TESTS

Shiqiang Deng, Lin Ye, Yiu-Wing Mai and Hong-Yuan Liu

*Centre for Advanced Materials Technology, Department of Mechanical & Mechatronic
Engineering, The University of Sydney, NSW 2006, Australia*

SUMMARY: Single fibre fragmentation tests of two carbon fibre/epoxy composite systems were conducted by continuously monitoring fibre fragments and applied stresses to determine the Weibull fibre strength parameters. It was shown that the measurement of the Weibull fibre strength parameters in the epoxy matrix is possible using single fibre fragmentation test. A linear relation between the logarithm of the average fibre fragment length and the logarithm of the maximum fibre axial stress was found prior to the saturation of fibre fragments. Discrepancy exists between the results obtained from the fragmentation tests and those from the extrapolation of conventional fibre tensile tests in air, which is attributed to the limitation of the Weibull weakest-link model and the fibre degradation in the specimen preparation process.

KEYWORDS: Weibull fibre strength parameters, single fibre fragmentation test, carbon fibre, epoxy, interface

INTRODUCTION

Among the micromechanical testing methods for evaluating fibre/matrix interfacial properties of fibre-reinforced composites, single fibre fragmentation test has attracted extensive attention since the method was introduced by Kelly and Tyson [1] because the fibre stress state in the test specimen is similar to that in the real composite and the fibre fragmentation phenomenon is sensitive to the level of fibre/matrix interfacial adhesion. However, for the interpretation of test results the fibre strength at the saturation state is very crucial because the direct measurement of the fibre tensile strength at the critical fibre length (commonly < 1 mm) is almost impossible using normal tensile testing methods. The value of the fibre tensile strength is usually obtained by testing a number of fibre specimens at several specified gauge lengths in air, then the results are extrapolated to the domain of the critical fibre fragment length using some statistical models such as the Weibull weakest-link model. However, the value of fibre strength at the critical fibre fragment length obtained in this way may differ from the actual *in situ* fibre strength. Therefore, the proper test methods are required to measure the *in situ* fibre tensile strength, so that more reasonable values of the interfacial properties could be obtained from the single fibre fragmentation tests. In this study single fibre fragmentation tests of two carbon fibre/epoxy composite systems were conducted by continuously monitoring the fibre fragments and the applied stresses to determine the Weibull fibre strength parameters within the range of the critical fibre length.

THEORY

The distribution function of the two-parameter Weibull model is commonly used to define the fibre strength parameters [2, 3]

$$P = 1 - \exp\left[-\left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_o(s)}\right)^m\right] \quad (1)$$

where P is the cumulative failure probability, σ is the applied stress, m is the Weibull shape parameter and $\sigma_o(s)$ is the local scale parameter with gauge length s . The Weibull Parameter m must be constant from one gauge length to another and the scale parameter $\sigma_o(s)$ is dependent on the gauge length s with the relation

$$\sigma_o(s) = s^{-\frac{1}{m}} \sigma_c \quad (2)$$

where σ_c is the global scale parameter for all gauge lengths. The cumulative failure probability P_i under a particular stress is approximated by

$$P_i = (n_i - 0.5) / n \quad (3)$$

where n_i is the number of fibres that have fractured at or below a stress and n is the total number of fibres tested. In practice, the plot of $\ln[-\ln(1-P)]$ versus $\ln(\sigma)$ is often used for a given fibre length to derive the Weibull shape parameter m and scale parameter $\sigma_o(s)$ from Eq. 1 since it yields a linear dependence with slope m . For different fibre lengths, the logarithmic form of Eq. 2 can be used to define m and σ_c

$$\ln[\sigma_o(s)] = \ln(\sigma_c) - \frac{1}{m} \ln(s) \quad (4)$$

Combining Eqs. 1 and 2 yields the following equation for the cumulative failure probability function

$$P = 1 - \exp\left[-s\left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_c}\right)^m\right] \quad (5)$$

The failure probability density function, $f(\sigma)$, can be obtained by differentiating Eq. 5 and it is given by

$$f(\sigma) = s \frac{m}{\sigma_c} \left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_c}\right)^{m-1} \exp\left[-s\left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_c}\right)^m\right] \quad (6)$$

There have been some efforts to obtain the fibre strength distribution and to study the “size effect” from single fibre fragmentation tests in recent years [4-6]. The fibre fragmentation phenomenon is viewed as a “multiple tensile test” with different gauge lengths, which obeys the Weibull weakest-link model [4, 5]. The average fibre tensile strength σ_f with a gauge length, s , is given by

$$\sigma_f = \int_0^{\infty} \sigma f(\sigma) d\sigma = \sigma_c s^{-\frac{1}{m}} \Gamma\left(1 + \frac{1}{m}\right) \quad (7)$$

where Γ is the gamma function. If the single fibre fragmentation tests are regarded as a series of tensile tests in which individual samples of various lengths are subjected to the same applied stress, the reverse form of Eq. 7 gives the relationship between the average fibre fragment length s and the fibre stress σ_f

$$s = \sigma_c^m \sigma_f^{-m} \left[\Gamma\left(1 + \frac{1}{m}\right) \right]^m \quad (8)$$

In Eq. 8, s and σ_f can be evaluated from the single fibre fragmentation tests by continuously monitoring the fibre fragments and the applied stress σ . A relationship between the fibre axial stress σ_f^z and the applied stress σ can be obtained assuming a perfect bonding between the fibre and the matrix [7]

$$\sigma_f^z(z) = \eta \left(\sigma - \sigma \frac{\cosh \sqrt{A_1} z}{\cosh \sqrt{A_1} L} \right) \quad (9)$$

where L is the half length of the fibre fragment, z is the distance from the middle point of the fibre fragment, and η and A_1 are constants related to Young's moduli and Poisson's ratios of the fibre and matrix as well as the geometry of the test specimen [7]. In Eq. 9 the maximum fibre axis stress occurs at the middle of the fibre fragment ($z=0$) where fibre breakage may happen, so that the maximum fibre axis stress is considered as the fibre fracture stress σ_f during the fibre fragmentation test.

The Young's modulus of the matrix, E_m , is normally not a constant during the whole fibre fragmentation process for most polymer resins, which was ignored in most previous studies. E_m should be dependent on the applied stress when it is used to calculate the fibre axis stress.

Based on Eq. 8, $\ln(s)$ is plotted versus $\ln(\sigma_f)$ to produce a straight line with the slope being $-m$. The Weibull scale parameter σ_c can then be calculated from the value of the intercept,

$$m \cdot \left[\ln \sigma_c + \ln \Gamma\left(1 + \frac{1}{m}\right) \right] \quad (10)$$

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Single fibre fragmentation tests of two model carbon fibre/epoxy composite systems (G34-700/Araldite-F and T700S/Araldite-F) were conducted on a Minimat testing machine (Polymer Laboratories Ltd., UK), which is installed on the sample stage of an optical microscope and controlled by a computer. G34-700 carbon fibres (Grafil Inc., USA) were supplied with two surface conditions, i.e. one without any surface treatment and the other treated using electrochemical oxidation and then coated with a thin layer of epoxy sizing (0.4% by mass). The "as received" T700S fibres were treated and sized by the manufacturer. Some of T700S fibres were washed in a methylethylketone (MEK) solution for 1 hour and then

dried for 2 hour in an oven at 200°C to remove the sizing. Fibre diameters were measured by a high resolution SEM. Test specimens, consisting of a single fibre embedded in the centre of a rubber mould filled with liquid epoxy resin, were pre-cured for 48 hours at ambient temperature and then post-cured at 120° C for 16 hours to avoid the influence of thermal residual stress produced by direct high temperature curing. The Young’s moduli of the fibre and the matrix were determined by the tensile tests. The carbon fibres used in this study have a constant Young’s modulus, but the matrix exhibits a non-linear stress-strain relationship (Fig. 1). Non-linear elastic theory was applied in this case and the stress-strain curve was divided into finite sections. A linear relation within each section is assumed and then the value of the matrix Young’s modulus, E_m , was obtained from the slope of the curve in the section.

Fig. 1 Typical tensile stress-strain curve of the single fibre fragmentation test

The gauge length of all specimens was 30 mm and a cross-head speed of 0.1 mm/min was applied for the fibre fragmentation tests. The fibre breaks and the relative applied stress readings were continuously recorded during the test until the saturation of the fragments was achieved. The Weibull fibre strength parameters obtained from single fibre fragmentation tests are shown in Table 1. A typical $\ln(s)-\ln(\sigma_f)$ curve obtained using Eq. 8 for the treated/sized G34-700 carbon/Araldite-F epoxy system is shown in Fig. 2. It can be seen that the data fit reasonably well a straight line before the saturation limit is approached, but after that a great deviation from linearity occurs. The main reason for the deviation from the Weibull statistical model when approaching the saturation limit is the influence of the “ineffective length”. This length represents the fibre portion in both ends of a fibre fragment where the axial stress is built up to the value of the peak fibre stress. When the fibre fragment is much longer than the critical fibre length, the ineffective length is relative small, compared to the whole fibre segment and its effect can be neglected. However, with the increase of the applied stress, some short fibre segments cannot be broken anymore because the fibre axial stress cannot be built up to the fibre fracture strength within these segments while the fibre fragmentation in some remaining long segments still proceeds until the lengths of all segments are equal to or less than the critical fibre length. Fig. 3 shows the variation of the fibre axial stress along the fibre fragment for several different fibre lengths ($2L$), estimated by Eq. 9. It can be clearly seen that when close to the saturation limit the ineffective length is

comparable to the whole fibre fragment and thus the linear relationship between $\ln(s)$ and $\ln(\sigma_f)$ does not exist anymore.

Fig. 2 A typical plot of $\ln(s)$ versus $\ln(\sigma_f)$ of single fibre fragmentation tests (treated/sized G34-700 carbon fibre/Araldite-F epoxy)

Single fibre tensile tests were also conducted for the carbon fibres based on the ASTM standard (ASTM D3379-75) and the Weibull weakest-link model was applied to analyse the results. The crosshead speed for all tests was 1 mm/min and five different gauge lengths were specified. Weibull fibre strength parameters tested in air using conventional tensile test method are listed in Table 2.

Fig.3 Plot of fibre axial stress (σ_f^z) as a function of axial distance (z) from fibre segment centre ($\sigma=50$ MPa; $E_f=240$ GPa; $E_m=1.75$ GPa)

The data obtained from six fragmentation specimens and the single fibre tensile results tested in air for treated/sized G34-700 carbon fibres are plotted together in Fig. 4. For T700S/Araldite-F systems, the similar results were obtained (Fig. 5). There is a good agreement between the values of the Weibull shape modulus obtained from the fragmentation tests and those from the conventional fibre tensile tests in air for treated/sized G34-700/Araldite-F and sized T700S/Araldite-F composite systems. However, discrepancy exists between the values of Weibull scale parameters as shown in Tables 1 and 2, Figs. 4 & 5. One of the reasons which cause the discrepancy is that the Weibull weakest-link model is only applicable over a limited length range. For long gauge lengths the chance of a low fracture stress due to accidental damage (i.e. due to rare defects which are not part of the normal defect population) becomes significant. Therefore, the size influence may be over-estimated if the extrapolation is made to a very short length as demonstrated by Dai and Piggott [8]. Another reason is considered to be the fibre degradation in the post-cure process at a high temperature. The post cure process was used in this study in the specimen preparation to reduce the influence of the matrix shrinkage during the direct curing at high temperature since extensive matrix shrinkage can cause misalignment and waviness of the fibre in the matrix. However, during the post curing at the high temperature the matrix expands much greater than the fibre does, so that a huge tensile stress (as large as 1.5 GPa) is exerted on the fibre, which increases the size of fibre flaws and even causes fibre fracture at some weak points. For untreated/unsized G34-700/Araldite-F and desized T700S/Araldite-F composite systems, discrepancy exists in both Weibull shape parameters and Weibull scale parameters between the two testing methods. This means that the assumption of perfect bonding between fibre and matrix may not be true for the two composite systems since extensive interfacial debonding may occur during the test after fibre fragmentation begins for the composite systems with weak fibre/matrix adhesion.

Table 1 Weibull strength parameters of single carbon fibres obtained from single fibre fragmentation tests

	G34-700 (Treated/ sized)	G34-700 (Untreated/ unsized)	T700S (Sized)	T700S (Desized)
Range of fibre fragments used, mm	10-0.4	10-0.8	7.5-0.7	7.5-1.0
Range of applied stress, MPa	30-50	30-45	30-58	30-55
Applied stress at saturation, MPa	53.4±1.6	48.9±3.4	59.1±1.0	56.7±3.1
Weibull shape parameter, <i>m</i>	4.8±1.2	3.2±1.2	4.8±1.4	3.3±0.6
Weibull scale parameter, σ_c GPa	4.3±0.4	5.3±0.7	8.5±1.2	9.2±1.3

Table 2 Weibull strength parameters of single carbon fibres tested in air

	Gauge length, s [mm]	Weibull shape parameter (local), m	Weibull scale parameter, $\sigma_0(s)$ [GPa]	Average tensile strength [GPa]	Weibull shape parameter (global), m	Weibull scale parameter, σ_0 [GPa]
	10	8.1	4.6	4.3±0.6		
	20	4.8	4.3	3.9±0.9		
G34-700 (Treated/sized)	30	6.4	3.9	3.6±0.6	4.3	8.1
	40	5.4	3.4	3.2±0.7		
	50	4.9	3.2	3.0±0.7		
	10	5.7	4.7	4.4±0.9		
	20	5.1	4.0	3.6±0.8		
G34-700 (Untreated/unsized)	30	5.2	3.8	3.5±0.7	5.5	7.1
	40	6.1	3.6	3.4±0.6		
	50	7.3	3.5	3.3±0.5		
	10	3.5	7.7	6.9±2.1		
	20	5.0	6.2	5.7±1.4		
T700S (Sized)	30	4.0	6.2	5.6±1.5	6.1	10.8
	40	3.7	6.0	5.4±1.6		
	50	4.0	5.8	5.3±1.4		
	10	3.8	7.0	6.3±1.6		
	20	4.0	6.3	5.7±1.6		
T700S (Desized)	30	3.4	5.9	5.3±1.5	5.9	10.4
	40	2.9	5.6	5.0±1.7		
	50	3.4	5.3	4.8±1.4		

Fig. 4 Plot of $\ln(s)$ versus $\ln(\sigma_f)$ of single fibre fragmentation specimens (treated/sized G34-700 carbon fibre/Araldite-F epoxy) in comparison with results of single fibre tensile tests in air

Fig. 5 Plot of $\ln(s)$ versus $\ln(\sigma_f)$ of single fibre fragmentation specimens (sized T700S carbon fibre/Araldite-F epoxy) in comparison with results of single fibre tensile tests in air

CONCLUSIONS

1. The measurement of the *in situ* fibre strength in the epoxy matrix is possible using single fibre fragmentation tests.
2. A linear relation between the logarithm of the average fibre fragment length and the logarithm of the maximum fibre axial stress is found before the saturation of fibre fragments is reached.
3. Discrepancy exists between the results obtained from the fragmentation tests and those from the extrapolations of conventional fibre tensile tests in air. This is considered to be associated with the limitation of the Weibull weakest-link model because it is only applicable over a limited length range. The fibre degradation in post-cure at the high temperature may also have a strong influence on the results.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors wish to thank the Australian Research Council for the continuing support of this study. Thanks are also due to Torayca Inc., Japan and Grafil Inc., USA for supplying the fibre materials. S. Deng is supported by Australian Overseas Postgraduate Scholarship (OPRS) and a Postgraduate Scholarship from the Department of Mechanical & Mechatronic Engineering at the University of Sydney.

REFERENCES

1. Kelly, A. and Tyson, W. R., "Tensile properties of fibre-reinforced metals: copper/tungsten and copper/molybdenum", *J. Mech. Phys. Solids* 13 (1965) 329.
2. Oshawa, T., Nakayama, A., Miwa, M. and Hasegawa, A., "Temperature dependence of the critical fibre length for the glass fibre-reinforced thermosetting resins", *J. Applied Polymer Science*, 22 (1978) 3203-12.
3. Watson, A. S. and Smith, R. L., "An examination of statistical theories for fibrous materials in the light of experimental data", *J. Mater. Sci.* 20 (1985) 3260-3270.
4. Wagner, H. D. and Eitan, A., "Interpretation of the fragmentation phenomenon in single-filament composite experiments", *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, 56 (1990) 1965-1967.
5. Yavin, B., Gallis, H. E., Scherf, J., Eitan, A. and Wagner, H. D., "Continuous monitoring of the fragmentation phenomenon in single fibre composite materials", *Polym. Compos.* 12 (1991) 436.
6. Goda, K., Park, J. M. and Netravali, A. N., "A new theory to obtain Weibull fibre strength parameters from a single-fibre composite test", *J. Materi. Sci.* 30 (1995) 2722.
7. Zhou, L., Kim, J. K., Baillie, C. and Mai, Yiu-Wing, "Stress transfer in the fibre fragmentation test: Part III. Effect of matrix cracking and interface debonding", *J. Compos. Materi.* 7 (1995) 881.
8. Dai, S. -R. and Piggott, M. R., "The strengths of carbon and kevlar fibres as a function of their lengths", *Composites Sci. Technol.*, 49 (1993) 81-87.